

Supporting Information

Electrospun PAN membrane loaded with AgInP₂Se₆ nanosheets for triboelectric energy harvesting

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Figure S1. Characterization of bulk $\text{AgInP}_2\text{Se}_6$: a) SEM micrograph with EDS mapping of elements and respective b) EDS spectrum.

Table S1. Quantification of elements (at.%) of prepared materials by SEM-EDS analysis.

Material	Element						
	C	N	Se	O	P	In	Ag
Bulk AgInP_2S_6	29.0*	-	41.8	1.1	13.3	7.0	7.7
exf- AgInP_2S_6	32.4*	-	38.4	2.7	11.6	7.3	7.7
exf- $\text{AgInP}_2\text{S}_6/\text{PAN}$	74.5	17.1	3.2	3.0	1.1	0.6	0.5

*The C signal corresponds to the contribution from the carbon tape used during the analysis.

Figure S2. Characterization of exf-AgInP₂Se₆: a) Digital photo of vacuum filtered exf-AgInP₂Se₆. b) Bright mode STEM micrograph of exfoliated material. c) STEM-HADF micrograph and respective mapping of elements for a representative exf-AgInP₂Se₆ sheet. d) EDS elemental spectrum of exf-AgInP₂Se₆ (obtained from powder material in C tape at 20 kV acceleration voltage). e) Histogram of measured sheets lateral size ($\langle L \rangle = 424 \pm 282$ nm).

Figure S3. Characterization of exf-AgInP₂Se₆/PAN: a) SEM micrograph and respective mapping of elements. b) HADF mode STEM micrograph for an example of PAN with exfoliated material and respective mapping of elements. Inset: histogram of the measured fibre diameter ($\varnothing = 1.24 \pm 0.43$ μm).

Figure S4. Triboelectric series of exf-AgInP₂Se₆/PAN: Comparison of output voltage (V_{oc}) generated by the device in configuration with various triboelectric materials such as polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), polyimide, polyethersulfone (PES), polyimide textile, polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), MoS₂-PDMS, graphene-textile, Cu textile, Ag textile, polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyacrylonitrile (PAN), and nitrile.

Figure S5. Electrical output performance of exf-AgInP₂Se₆/PAN-enabled TENG: a) Open circuit voltage, V_{oc} , b) short-circuit current, I_{sc} and c) open-circuit charge, Q_{oc} .

Figure S6. Triboelectric response of the exf-AgInP₂Se₆/PAN-TENG under deformation: a) Schematic illustration of the placement of the exf-AgInP₂Se₆/PAN layer within the TENG setup. b) Open circuit voltage, V_{oc} , c) short-circuit current, I_{sc} and d) open-circuit charge output, Q_{oc} , measured in four configurations, namely I – flat (before and after deformation), II – bent, and III – compressed configuration.

Figure S7. Cumulative charge harvesting: Open-circuit charge output, Q_{oc} , of the exf-AgInP₂Se₆/PAN-TENG over time in the parallel configuration.

Figure S8. Humidity test of the exf-AgInP₂Se₆/PAN-TENG: Electrical output performance of the device measured under exposure to different humidity levels, namely 20–70%: **a)** open circuit voltage, V_{oc} , **b)** short-circuit current, I_{sc} , and **c)** open-circuit charge, Q_{oc} . The red curve corresponds to the TENG output measured under ambient (room) humidity conditions, while the black curve represents the output measured at room humidity after the device had been exposed to 70% humidity.